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Social connectedness and dimensions of emerging adulthood among young adults in India

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Abstract

The current study investigates the relationship between social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e. identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between, and experimentation/possibilities among young adults in India. The study employs a quantitative approach, utilizing self-report inventories to gather data from 207 (N=207) participants aged 18-25 years in Indian cities. The measurement tools used were the Social Connectedness Scale-R (SCS-R) devised by Lee and Robbins (1995) and the Inventory for Dimensions of Emerging Adulthood (Revised) devised by Reifman et al (2007). The Spearman correlation results showed that there was a positive correlation between SCS-R and Experimentation/Possibilities as well as a positive relationship between Social Connectedness and Self-Focused. However, there was no statistically significant correlation found between Social Connectedness and the dimension of identity exploration and feeling in-between. Regression analysis demonstrated that social connectedness had a significant influence on the dimensions of experimentation/possibilities and self-focused. The study also showed that there were no differences on social connectedness and dimensions of emerging adulthood based on gender.

Keywords: Social Connectedness; Emerging Adulthood; Young Adults; Identity exploration; Social Support

1. Introduction

The transition from adolescence to adulthood is a critical and complex stage of life, which involves significant changes in physical, psychological, and social aspects. During this transitional period, there is a gradual progress towards greater maturity alongside the expectation of taking responsibility for one's own decisions and being able to make an independent choice in pursuit of self-reliance [2]. This time is when individuals are faced with multifaceted changes which will set the stage for becoming more independent and self-sufficient. Arnett suggested that this period between the ages of 18 and 25 be classified as a "distinct phase" called emerging adulthood (EA). The notion of "emerging adulthood," which was developed by psychologist Jeffrey Arnett [2] describes it as "Having left the dependency of childhood and adolescence, and having not yet entered the enduring responsibilities that are normative in adulthood, emerging adults often explore a variety of possible life directions in love, work, and worldviews". In other words, this is the period of time when people prefer to think of themselves as neither fully grown adults nor too old to be adolescents. The whole idea of Emerging Adulthood is based on Arnett's theory who lays out the dimensions of EA and has proposed that EA is characterized by five distinctive features: The age of identity explorations: Emerging adulthood is a time of profound self-discovery and identity exploration. It is during this stage that individuals embark on a quest to define who they are, what they believe, and what values they hold. The age of instability: It is the age of change and change is itself unsettling, and some individuals may lack (or feel they lack) the confidence and wherewithal to succeed. This facet of emerging adulthood refers to the age of instability. The self-focused age: Emerging adulthood is characterized by a pronounced period of self-focus. It is a time when individuals prioritize self-exploration, personal growth, and the pursuit of individual goals. The age of feeling in-between: Emerging adulthood is the age of feeling in-between because the majority of emerging adults feel they are no longer adolescents but not yet fully adults. The age of possibilities: It is

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the age of possibilities because it tends to be viewed as a period filled with optimism, characterized by the perception of numerous potential partners, career prospects, societal involvements, and other obligations being within reach. [4].

During the phase of adolescence, young individuals encounter diverse transformations in their social connections, which present them with chances to foster and manifest their personal and social identities, as well as investigate their autonomy [24]. The primary role of relationships is to provide support for young people as they navigate through adolescence and the transition to adulthood. Thus, it is essential to build and maintain strong family relationships and resources. Numerous studies emphasize the importance of social support [19] as a significant protective element for emerging adults undergoing specific transitions.

Social connectedness, which plays a critical role in shaping the experiences and outcomes of emerging adults. It is defined as "the subjective awareness of being in a close relationship with the social world" [13]. To put it simply, social connectedness encompasses our interactions with others and how we perceive ourselves in relation to these connections and associations. In college-age populations, a sense of social connectedness has been linked to increased social engagement, positive perceptions of others, ease in forming relationships [16], enhanced social skills and psychological well-being [23], and higher levels of self-esteem [16].

Numerous empirical studies have consistently demonstrated that social connectedness plays a crucial role in the exploration and development of identity among emerging adults [22]. Supportive relationships provide a nurturing environment for individuals to examine their values, beliefs, and personal aspirations, ultimately contributing to the establishment of a stable sense of self. For instance, Erikson [10] argued that understanding one's roles and connections to the broader community is vital for healthy psychosocial development. A strong sense of social connectedness, rooted in the fundamental need for belonging, connection, and a sense of relatedness [6], whether fostered within educational institutions, family units, or peer groups, may provide the "basic trust" that fosters an individual's self-confidence in relation to the world. This trust enables individuals to take risks, explore various options, and ultimately make commitments. Erikson [9] posits that supportive relationships, such as social connectedness, are essential for developing trust in others and in oneself (i.e., confidence), which in turn propels individuals to actively engage in the formation of their identity (i.e., reducing feelings of being "lost").

In line with clinical observations, it was discovered in the research that females who encounter a lack in social connectedness tend to display reduced levels of self-esteem, decreased satisfaction in social interactions, increased perception of environmental threats, and diminished inclination to establish a social identity within social contexts [13].

A study found that there was a positive correlation between parent relationship closeness and self-focus and perceived possibilities among male participants, while also negatively correlating with instability. On the other hand, male peer relationship closeness was positively associated with identity exploration, possibilities, self-focus, and feeling in between. Among female participants, parent relationship closeness was positively correlated with perceived possibilities, self-focus, and feeling in between, and negatively correlated with instability. Additionally, female peer relationship closeness was positively associated with possibilities and self-focus, and negatively associated with instability. It was found that peer relationships contributed more to the emerging adult experiences of men, while parent relationships contributed more to the experiences of women, except in the case of instability. The study suggests that secure parent relationships may serve as a protective factor against feelings of instability and foster a sense of possibilities and self-focus [21].

2. Material and methods

2.1 Research Design

The research design adopts a quantitative correlational research design to investigate the relationship and impact of Social Connectedness and Dimensions of Emerging Adulthood among Young Adults in India.

2.2 Statement of the problem

The current study investigates the relationship between social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood, including identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between, and possibilities among young adults in India. The study also explores the influence of social connectedness on each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between, and experimentation/possibilities.

2.3 Objective of the study

- O1- To study the relationship between social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e. identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between, and experimentation/possibilities among young adults in India.
- O2- To study if social connectedness has an influence on any of the dimensions of emerging adulthood (Identity exploration, experimentation/possibilities, self-focus, feeling in between).
- O3- To study the gender differences on social connectedness among young adults in India.
- O4- To study the gender differences on dimensions of emerging adulthood among young adults in India.

2.4 Hypothesis

- H₀1- There is no significant relationship between social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between and experimentation/possibilities.
- H₀2- There is no significant influence of social connectedness on each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between and experimentation/possibilities.
- H₀3- There is no significant difference in social connectedness based on gender.
- H₀4- There is no significant difference on how males and females differ in each dimension of emerging adulthood.

2.5 Operational Definitions

2.5.1 Social Connectedness

Social connectedness is a sense of belonging to a group, family, or community. It's about the relationships people have with each other and their engagement with the broader community.

2.5.2 Emerging Adulthood

The time of life roughly between ages 18-25 can be considered a “distinct period” called emerging adulthood (EA). Essentially, this is a time when individuals tend to consider themselves too old to be adolescents, but not yet full-fledged adults.

2.6 Sample and Techniques

The present study consists of a sample of 207 (N=207) Young Adults from different cities of India between the age of 18-25 years. The data collection employed a non-probability convenience sampling technique to select participants for this particular research study. The data collection method involves self-report inventories, where participants responded to structured questionnaires in a google form.

2.7 Tools for the study

2.7.1 Social Connectedness Scale -R (SCS-R)

The scale by Lee and Robbins (1995) measures the degree of interpersonal closeness that an individual experiences in his or her social world (e.g., friends, peers, society) as well as the degree of difficulty in maintaining this sense of closeness. This self-report scale consists of eight items that are assessed using a 6-point Likert-type scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The scale demonstrates good reliability, with high internal consistency of items ($\alpha = .91$) and test-retest reliability over a 2-week period ($r = .96$).

2.7.2 Inventory for Dimensions of Emerging Adulthood

Developed by Reifman, Arnett, & Colwell in 2007. IDEA- R is a self-report inventory which consists of 21 items divided across 4 dimensions of emerging adulthood i.e a time of identity exploration, experimentation/possibilities, self-focus, and feeling in-between. The scale requires us to think about this time in your life. By “time in your life,” we are referring to the present time, plus the last few years that have gone by, and the next few years to come, as you see them. Internal consistency (alpha) reliability coefficients for the subscales were generally strong, between .70-.85. Test-retest reliability correlations (over a one-month interval) ranged from .64-.76, with the exception of the “feeling in-between” subscale (.37).

2.8 Geographical area

This research includes individuals from all over India.

2.9 Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals belonging to the age group of 18-25 years.
- Individuals belonging to cities in India.
- Participants should have sufficient proficiency in the English language.
- Individuals not diagnosed with any psychological disorder or intellectual disability.

2.10 Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals who do not give consent to participate in the study.
- Individuals who are currently seeking medical treatment for any disease or disorder.
- Individuals residing outside of India will be excluded from the study.
- Individuals who are currently seeking medical treatment for any disease or disorder.

2.11 Research ethics followed-

- Participants read and agreed to an informed consent form before answering the survey questions.
- Participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality of the responses they provided.
- Participants had the right to withdraw from the survey at any point.
- The data was handled only by the researchers solely for research purposes.
- The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association

2.12 Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed using the IBM SPSS software. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, and standard deviation, were computed for preliminary data analysis. Spearman rho's correlation was conducted to assess the relationship between the study variables. Linear regression analysis was used to understand the impact of social connectedness on each dimension of Emerging Adulthood. Along with that, Mann-Whitney U test was used to find out the gender differences in the study variables.

3. Results

The final data was analyzed using statistical software SPSS 25. A normality test was used to determine whether the sample data has been drawn from a normally distributed population. It was found that at histogram and normal probability plot an outlier has caused the non-normality and thus the values were significant. Hence non-parametric statistics were used for the entire study.

Variable	n	M	SD	Min	Max
Social Connectedness	207	75.657	15.576	25.00	117.00
Experimentation /Possibilities	--	16.816	2.5647	10.00	20.00
Self-Focused	--	20.444	2.9272	11.00	24.00
Identity Exploration	--	23.676	3.1525	14.00	28.00
Feeling In-Between	--	9.7874	1.6438	5.00	12.00

Figure 1 Descriptive statistics of the variables (Mean and Standard Deviation)

According to figure 1, which shows the descriptive statistics for the study variables: Social Connectedness and Dimensions of Emerging Adulthood, based on a sample size of 207. The data suggests that on average, For Social Connectedness, the Mean= 75.65, Standard Deviation= 15.57. For each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e. Experimentation/Possibilities the Mean= 16.81 and Standard Deviation= 2.56, Self-focused the Mean= 20.44 and Standard Deviation= 2.92, Identity Exploration the Mean= 23.67 and Standard Deviation= 3.15 and Feeling In-between the Mean= 9.78 and Standard Deviation= 1.64.

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4
Social Connectedness	207	75.657	15.576	--			
Experimentation /Possibilities	--	16.816	2.5647	.222**			
Self-Focused	--	20.444	2.9272	.242**	.590**		
Identity Exploration	--	23.676	3.1525	.113	.565**	.622**	
Feeling In-Between	--	9.7874	1.6438	.037	.383**	.416**	.561**

Figure 2 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

According to Figure 2, which denotes the correlation between Social Connectedness and each dimension of Emerging Adulthood i.e. Experimentation/Possibilities, Self-Focused, Identity Exploration and Feeling In-between. The correlation was calculated and was significant at 0.01 level. The Spearman correlation results showed that there was a positive correlation between Social Connectedness and Experimentation/Possibilities ($r=0.222^{**}$, $p=0.01$). The results also showed a positive correlation between Social Connectedness and Self-Focused ($r=0.242^{**}$, $p=0.01$). These results suggest that as when an individual experiences high social connectedness, there is also an increase in self-focus as well as experimentation and possibilities. However, there was no statistically significant correlation found between Social Connectedness and the dimension of identity exploration and feeling. Therefore, these results partially accept null hypothesis H_01 , as social connectedness appears to be positively associated with two out of the four dimensions focused in the hypothesis.

Variables	Unstandardized		Standardized	Model Summary
	Coefficients		Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	β (Beta)	
Social Connectedness	.031	.011	.190	F = 7.651 t = 2.766 Sig = .006 R = .190 R square = .036

Dependent Variable: Experimentation/Possibilities

Figure 3 Linear regressions analysis scores between Social Connectedness and Experimentation/Possibilities

Figure 3 shows the results of linear regression analysis and explains to what extent social connectedness impacts experimentation/possibilities dimension of emerging adulthood as evidenced by the F statistic of 7.651 ($p = .006$). The unstandardized coefficient (B) for social connectedness was .031, suggesting that on average, a one-unit increase in Social Connectedness corresponds to a .031-unit increase in experimentation/possibilities. The standardized coefficient β (Beta) of 0.190 implies a modest positive relationship between Social Connectedness and Experimentation/Possibilities. The t statistic of 2.766 supports the individual significance of social connectedness. The

R value of .190 signifies a weak positive correlation, and the R square value of .036 indicates approximately 3.6% of the variability in experimentation/possibilities can be explained by social connectedness.

Variables	Unstandardized		Standardized	Model Summary
	Coefficients		Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	β (Beta)	
Social Connectedness	.037	.013	.199	F = 8.457 t = 2.908 Sig = .004 R = .199 R square = .040

Dependent Variable: Self Focused

Figure 4 Linear regressions analysis scores between Social Connectedness and Self-Focused

Figure 4 shows the results of linear regression analysis and explains to what extent social connectedness impacts self-focused dimension of emerging adulthood as evidenced by the F statistic of 8.457 ($p = .004$). The unstandardized coefficient (B) for social connectedness was .037, suggesting that on average, a one-unit increase in Social Connectedness corresponds to a .037-unit increase in self-focused. The standardized coefficient β (Beta) of 0.199 implies a modest positive relationship between Social Connectedness and self-focused. The t statistic of 2.908 supports the individual significance of social connectedness. The R value of .199 signifies a weak positive correlation, and the R square value of .040 indicates approximately 4% of the variability in self-focused can be explained by social connectedness. Therefore, these results from regression analysis partially accept null hypothesis H_{02} which states that there is a significant effect of social connectedness on each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e identity exploration, self-focus, feeling in-between and experimentation/possibilities.

Variable	Gender	n	Mean	SD	SE	t	df	p
Social Connectedness	Male	92	76.34	15.80	1.64	.535	204	.593
	Female	114	75.17	15.48	1.45			

Figure 4 Independent t- test for differences in social connectedness based on gender

Figure 4, shows results of independent t test which was conducted to find out significant differences on social connectedness based on gender. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the distribution of social connectedness between males ($M=76.34, SD=15.80$) and females ($M=75.17, SD=15.48$). The t value was found to be =.535 with a corresponding p value of .593 ($p>0.05$) which shows that there does not exist a statistically significant Gender difference among Indian Young Adults with regard to Social Connectedness. Therefore, these results accept the null hypothesis H_{03} which states that there is no significant difference on social connectedness based on gender.

Variable	Gender	n	Mean	SD	SE	t	df	p
Experimentation/Possibilities	Male	92	16.88	2.647	.275	.325	204	.746
	Female	114	16.76	2.518	.235			
Self-Focused	Male	--	20.08	2.996	.312	-1.54	204	.124
	Female		20.71	2.861	.267			
Identity Exploration	Male	--	23.35	3.022	.315	-1.25	204	.212
	Female		23.91	3.252	.304			
Feeling In-Between	Male	--	9.61	1.682	.175	-1.30	204	.192
	Female		9.92	1.613	.151			

Figure 5 Independent t- test for differences in each dimension of emerging adulthood based on gender

According to Figure 5, results of independent t test which was conducted to find out significant differences in dimensions of emerging adulthood based on gender. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the distribution of emerging adulthood between males and female. For experimentation/possibilities, the results for males (M=16.88, SD=2.64) and females (M=16.76, SD=2.51). The t value was found to be =.325 with a corresponding p value of .746 ($p>0.05$). For self-focused, the results for males (M=20.08, SD=2.99) and females (M=20.71, SD=2.86). The t value was found to be = -1.54 with a corresponding p value of .124 ($p>0.05$). For Identity exploration, the results for males (M=23.35, SD=3.02) and females (M=23.91, SD=3.25). The t value was found to be = -1.25 with a corresponding p value of .212 ($p>0.05$). For feeling in-between, the results for males (M=9.61, SD=1.68) and females (M=9.92, SD=1.61). The t value was found to be = -1.30 with a corresponding p value of .192 ($p>0.05$). These results shows that there does not exist a statistically significant Gender difference among Indian Young Adults with regard to Dimensions of Emerging Adulthood. Therefore, these results accept the null hypothesis H_04 which states that there is no significant difference on dimensions of emerging adulthood based on gender.

4. Discussion

The present study aims to understand social connectedness and its effect on each dimension of emerging adulthood i.e. Experimentation/Possibilities, Self-Focused, Identity Exploration and Feeling In-Between. We found positive associations between social connectedness and experimentation/possibilities as well as social connectedness and self-focus. These findings are similar to that of previous research that suggests that female and male peer relationship closeness was positively associated with possibilities and self-focus, and it was negatively associated with instability. Both types of relationships are also positively associated with focusing on oneself and perceiving the emerging adult years as a time of possibilities. Viewed collectively, these findings support the idea that relationships shape subjective emerging adult experiences deeply [21]. One study suggested that family interactions could facilitate a clear understanding of an adolescent's developing sense of self, potentially providing them with the confidence and skills to explore beyond the confines of the family [11]. Not only familial relationships, but connectedness towards peers also affect one's identity by helping an individual successfully negotiate developmental crises [8].

Understanding the complex interplay between social connectedness and identity exploration requires considering various contextual factors such as socio-economic status, substance use, well-being which could be interfering with the association between these two variables. For example, family socioeconomic status in late childhood emerged as a significant predictor of positive development in emerging adulthood. This finding is consistent with previous research suggesting that children who live in poorly resourced environments experience substantial developmental deficits [12]. Children growing up in higher socioeconomic status families are likely to have a greater capacity to take advantage of neighborhood resources such as social cohesion [7], and opportunities for relationships and activities that support their needs [17]. Constructing a stable identity and a feeling of being in-between adolescent and adult role expectations can be confusing and challenging. As a result, some emerging adults may use alcohol in an effort to alleviate identity confusion or embrace the increased personal freedom associated with this time of life to experiment or "try on" different behaviors and activities, particularly those associated with adulthood, such as alcohol use.

The findings of this study hypothesized that there is no significant difference on social connectedness among young adults based on gender. One study clarified these gender differences and reported that connectedness in men is not

different from connectedness in women when motivation for communion is distinguished from agency. It was also found that when college students were directly asked about their perceived closeness to others, there were no gender differences in their responses [18]. According to a study, both genders have a desire for social connectedness, although women prioritize intimacy and physical closeness, whereas men prioritize social comparison. However, women derive fulfillment from relationships that involve physical closeness, as it provides a reliable alliance, whereas men value relationships that emphasize social comparison, as it reassures their worth. These findings are consistent with previous research that suggests women are more socially connected through intimate relationships, while men seek connectedness through reassurance of their individual worth [15].

An additional finding was that there were no significant differences on how males and females differ in each dimension of emerging adulthood. However, there is limited literature that has conducted comprehensive comparisons of each dimension of emerging adulthood with respect to gender. The majority of research in this area has primarily concentrated on identity formation. Some studies suggest that there is a higher likelihood for young females to be at a more advanced stage in the process of identity development, specifically in the categories of identity achievement and moratorium. Conversely, it is more common for young males to fall into the categories of foreclosed and diffused identities. A similar pattern was observed in a study conducted in Northern India, which included adolescents and emerging adults [20]. However, another study found no significant differences in the development of identity between emerging-adult females and males [1].

5. Conclusion

In sum, our study has shed light into the associations found between social connectedness and various elements of emerging adulthood among young adults in India. It should be highlighted that we have established positive associations between social connectedness and two dimensions - experimentation/possibilities and self-focus. These findings are consistent with previous research that suggests that supportive peer relationships contribute to a sense of possibilities and self-focus during this stage of development. However, interestingly, our study has revealed no significant correlations between social connectedness and identity exploration or feeling in-between. This suggests a nuanced interplay between social relationships and identity development. Furthermore, our investigation has revealed no significant gender differences in social connectedness or the experience of dimensions related to emerging adulthood. This challenges traditional beliefs regarding gender-specific preferences in social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood. These findings align with emerging research that indicates a more uniform pattern of social connectedness and each dimension of emerging adulthood across genders. As a whole, our study emphasizes the complexity of social connectedness and dimensions of emerging adulthood, underscoring the importance of considering cultural and contextual factors in future research and interventions aimed at promoting positive developmental outcomes among young adults.

However, the limitations of the present study should be taken into consideration. The findings, although informative regarding emerging adulthood, require further attention to address several limitations. Firstly, enhancing the generalizability of the findings would have been possible with a larger sample size and a sample population representing the majority of cities in India. This research predominantly included participants from Pune, Mumbai, and Bengaluru. Secondly, this study focused solely on the context of social connectedness when examining emerging adulthood, neglecting the potential influence of other factors.

The future direction of research in Indian context should encompass a comprehensive exploration of demographic factors, including socio-economic status, educational attainment and occupational status. Moreover, it is suggested for further researchers to delve into other variables that encompass around the health and well-being of individuals such as use of alcohol and substance, mental well-being and health concerns. Furthermore, a mixed approach combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies would have provided deeper insights into the experiences of emerging adults in India. Lastly, future research should also investigate how emerging adulthood is experienced across genders in India, as there is limited empirical evidence on the variations of these dimensions across different genders.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to report.

Statement of ethical approval

As this study was done for dissertation purpose, approval was taken from the college.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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